

A Study on Mechanical Properties of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ Whisker Reinforced Aluminum Composites

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Abstract

In this study, $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker reinforced Al matrix composites by P/M method were metallurgically investigated from the viewpoint of mechanical and physical properties.

Homogeneous distribution of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker in Al matrix was found to be dependent upon Al powder size. Ni coating on whisker approved to be effective for the improvement of the room temperature strength of specimens, fabricated and thermal exposed, respectively. The room temperature strength of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ /Al composites increased with an increase of whisker content up to 20 vol. percent. The elevated temperature strength of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ /Al composites was much higher than that of pure aluminium although the strength of the composites decreases with increasing temperature. Hardness increased with increasing $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker content. Coefficient of thermal expansion also decreased proportionally with increasing $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker content.

1. Introduction

It is well known that whisker reinforced metals exhibit such desirable characteristic as high-specific strength and stiffness, high temperature capability, and high wear resistance. (1-3) SiC whisker reinforced Al alloy composite have many interesting properties which are attractive for aircraft structural application. However this materials also have some limitations, particularly low tensile ductilities and low fracture toughness. In addition, the machining of SiC whisker reinforced Al alloy composites is very difficult because of presence of the extremely hard, abrasive, ceramic SiC whiskers in a soft matrix. Compared with SiC whiskers reinforced Al alloy composites, $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker reinforced Al composites can be machined easily with ordinary tools because $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker is not as hard as SiC whisker. Futhermore, $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker have a potential for application in commercial fields because of the very cheap price.

Previous work (4) for this whisker indicated that during the fabtication of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker reinforced Al alloy by squeeze casting, chemical reaction between the whisker and molten Al occurs. In this case, it is difficult to improve the mechanical properties of the composites. Therefore, it is

necessary to fabricate the composites with a moderate volume fraction of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker. Using powder metallurgy method, it is possible to fabricate sound composites at lower temperature than at that which the chemical reaction between the whisker and aluminum might become active. However, there are little reports concerning the $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker reinforced aluminum by P/M method. T.Imai et al (5) showed that the strength of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker reinforced Al composites, which compacted in a tube and extruded at 500 to 578 °C, increased proportionally with volume fraction of the whiskers up to $V_f=40\%$. P/M process conditions appeared to be not obviously written in the above report.

The purpose of this paper is to study metallurgically for feasibility of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker/Al composites by powder metallurgy method from the view point of mechanical and physical properties.

2. Experimental Procedure

2-1. Materials

As described in table 1, $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker was used as reinforcement. Commercial Al powder containing 98 wt% of -325 mesh size was used as matrix.

2-2. Fabrication Process

Pure Al powder was mixed with whisker in an Sodium Oleate solution by the use of ultrasonic apparatus and then dried. Subsequently the mixture showed in Fig. 1 was cold-pressed and then compacted by hot-pressing under the pressure of 100 MPa in an argon atmosphere. Fig.2 illustrates the P/M process flow to produce $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker/Al composites. The compactions with the rectangular type (80mmx32mmx13mm) have whisker volume fraction of 0,10,20,30 and 40%, respectively. In addition, specimens with 20 vol. percent whisker was made to investigate for the effects on powder size and electroless Ni-coating for whisker in $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ /Al composites, respectively; the one is specimen with Al matrix containing 75 wt% of -325 mesh, the other is specimen reinforced with electroless Ni-coated whisker.

2-3. Tensile Tests

Tensile tests were carried out in the temperature range R.T. to 400 °C. The rectangular coupon specimens (80x15x3 mm) of unreinforced pure Al, whisker/Al composites and Ni coated whisker /Al composites were machined into tensile test pieces as shown in Figure 3. All tensile tests were conducted on an Instron-type testing machine, equipped with electrical furnace, at a cross head moving rate of 0.5 mm/min. Brinell hardness was measured related with the microstructure. Measurements for coefficient of thermal expansion was carried out by the use of dilatometer (Naruse-Kajakukikai).

2-4. Metallography and Fractography

Metallographic observation for microstructures of Al matrix and whisker distribution in specimens was carried out by means of optical microscopy. After the tests, the fracture surface of specimens was examined with a SEM.

3. Result and Discussion

Microstructures for whisker distribution in $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ /Al composites with various Al powder size are presented in Fig.4 (a) and (b). In optical microscopy, $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker appears to be black in contrast to white part of Al matrix. Whisker distribution in Al matrix containing 98% of

-325mesh(fine powder) appeared to be homogeneous as shown Fig.4 (a). However, whisker distribution in Al matrix containing 75% of -325mesh(coarse powder) was found to be inhomogeneous because entangled whisker rich region (black part) is surrounded large Al matrix with about 50 μm size as shown in Fig.4 (b). This microstructural inhomogeneity may contribute to the scatter and the drop in mechanical properties as reported in previous paper. (6)

Fig.5 illustrates S-S curves of room temperature tensile strength in specimens with different Al powder size. This plot shows that strength and fracture strain of specimen with coarse powder. As shown in fracture surfaces of Fig.6 (a) and (b), specimen with fine powder reveals dimple pattern characterizing ductile fracture, whereas specimen with coarse powder reveals brittle fracture mode in entangled whisker-rich region. Here, specimen with coarse powder appeared to fail in a brittle manner, resulting from that crack propagates through brittle whisker rich region under tensile stress. Therefore, it is considered that whisker distribution depends on matrix particle size, and is one of the most important factor affecting ductility and strength.

Fig.7 shows room temperature tensile strength of specimen with $\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot 6\text{TiO}_2$ whisker. Tensile strength value increases with an increase of whisker vol. percent up to 20 vol. percent. The tensile strength increase was probably caused by closer packing of the reinforcement and smaller interwhisker spacing in the matrix as presented in previous work. (7) However, it is observed that as the whisker content reaches 30 to 40 vol. percent, the value of tensile strength does not almost increase. Thus, the drastic downfall of reinforcing effect may be attributed to poor bonding between whisker and Al matrix at interface. It is noted from Fig.8 that density of specimen decreases with increasing vol. percent of whisker. Especially, specimen with 40 vol. percent of whisker shows relatively low density of 97.5%. The density decreases due to increasing vol. percent of whisker means an increase of microvoid formed by poor bonding between whisker and Al matrix. Consequently, microvoid roles as stress concentration riser and is detrimental to tensile stress and ductility in whisker/Al composites. Therefore, it is considered that mechanical property in whisker reinforced Al composites largely depends upon the degree of wettability at whisker-Al matrix interface.

In this study, electroless Ni coating on whisker surface was attempted in order to improve wettability and control chemical reaction at $\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot 6\text{TiO}_2$ whisker and Al matrix. It is noted from Fig.9 that room temperature strength of specimen with Ni-coated whisker is superior to that of specimen with uncoated whisker. This would cause by improvement of wettability accompanied with interdiffusion between Ni coating layer and Al matrix during fabricating at 640 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The Ni coating effect on chemical reaction in specimen exposed at 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 50h is presented in Fig.10. From this figure, room tensile strength of specimen with Ni-coated whisker appeared to be superior to that of specimen with uncoated whisker. After etching Al matrix with NaOH solution, results for SEM observations for whisker surface is presented Fig.11. Whisker surface of specimen with uncoated whisker seems to be considerably rougher than that of specimen with Ni-coated whisker. Rough layer of whisker surface may be considered to be reaction zone formed between whisker and Al matrix during thermal exposure. Ni-coating layer on whisker appeared to role as diffusion barrier for chemical reaction between $\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot 6\text{TiO}_2$ whisker and Al matrix and improve wettability at $\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot 6\text{TiO}_2$ whisker-Al matrix interface.

Fig.12 shows tensile strength of $\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot 6\text{TiO}_2$ whisker/Al composites at elevated temperatures. Elevated temperature tensile strength in all specimens tended to decrease as test temperature increases. Especially strength of

specimen with $K_2O_6TiO_2$ whisker appeared to be considerably superior to that of unreinforced Al matrix at $400^\circ C$. The tensile strength of composites with the vol. percent 30 was 180 MPa at $200^\circ C$ and 130 MPa at $400^\circ C$. From the above results, it is concluded that the strength of $K_2O_6TiO_2$ whisker/Al composites is significantly improved by the addition of $K_2O_6TiO_2$ whisker especially at elevated temperatures. It was observed in Fig.13 that Brinell hardness also increases with an increase of vol. percent of $K_2O_6TiO_2$ whisker that shows the higher hardness value compared with soft Al matrix. Fig.14 shows result for coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) in $K_2O_6TiO_2$ /Al composites. From this plot CTE decreases proportionally with increasing $K_2O_6TiO_2$ whisker content. Specimen with 40 vol. percent whisker shows CTE value of $12 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ C$. This value is about half compared with unreinforced pure Al.

Conclusions.

This investigation led to the following conclusions.

1. Homogeneous distribution of $K_2O_6TiO_2$ whisker in Al matrix was found to be dependent upon Al powder size.
2. Ni coating on whisker appeared to be effective for the improvement of the room temperature strength of specimens, fabricated and thermal exposed, respectively.
3. The room temperature strength of $K_2O_6TiO_2$ /Al composites increase with an increase of whisker content up to 20 vol. percent. The elevated temperature strength of $K_2O_6TiO_2$ /Al composites was much higher than that of pure Al although the strength of the composites decreased with increasing temperature.
4. Hardness increases with increasing $K_2O_6TiO_2$ whisker content. In addition, coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) also decreases proportionally with increasing $K_2O_6TiO_2$ whisker content. Consequently, specimen with 40 vol. percent whisker showed CTE value of $12 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ C$ for pure Al matrix with CTE of $23.6 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ C$.

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Table. 1 Properties of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$

Average Length	20-30 μm
Average Radius	0.1-0.3 μm
Density	3.58 (g/cm^3)
Tensile Strength	700 kg/mm^2
Elastic Modulus	2.8×10^4 kg/mm^2
Melting Point	1300-1350°C
Electrical Resistance	3.3×10^{15} Ωcm
Thermal Expansion Coefficient	6.8×10^{-6} /°C

Fig.1 Appearance of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ whisker preform mixed with Al powder containing (a) 98 weight pct. of -325 mesh (b) 75 weight pct. of -325 mesh.

Fig.2 Process flowchart for P/M fabrication of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ Whisker/Al Composites.

Fig.3 Design of tensile test specimen.

Fig.4 Microstructure of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ / pure Al composites with Al powder of (a) 98 weight pct. of -325mesh (b) 75 weight pct. of -325 mesh.

Fig.5 Stress-Strain curve for $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ / pure Al Composites with various Al Powder size.

Fig.6 Fractography of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ /pure Al composites with different Al powder size. (a) fine Al powder (b) coarse Al powder.

Fig.7 Room Temperature Tensile Strength vs. vol fraction in $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ Whisker/pure Al Composite.

Fig. 8 Variation of Density with Whisker volume fraction in $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ Whisker/pure Al Composites.

Fig. 9 Stress-Strain curve for $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ /pure Al Composites thermal exposed at $500^\circ C$ for 50 hr.

Fig. 10 R.T Tensile Strength of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ /pure Al Composites exposed at $500^\circ C$ for 50 hr in vacuum.

Fig.11 Whisker morphology of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ /pure Al composites exposed at $500^\circ C$ for 50 hr. (a) Ni-coated (b) uncoated.

Fig.12 Tensile Strength of $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ Whisker/pure Al Composite at elevate temperatures.

Fig. 13 Brinell Hardness vs. volume fraction in $K_2O \cdot 6TiO_2$ Whisker/Al composites.